

PREVALENCE OF HYPERTENSIVE DISORDERS OF PREGNANCY

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Annotation: The incidence of preeclampsia in hospital practice in India varies from 5% to 15%, and that of eclampsia is about 1.5%.⁷ In India, over the years, from 1976 to 2014, the risk of eclampsia ranges from 0.179 to 5%, with the average being 1.5%.⁸ Every year, over 5.2 million women die from pregnancy-related complications worldwide.⁹ With an estimated 62,000–77,000 deaths each year, HDP account for approximately 18.1% of maternal mortality.^{10–12} Pregnant women in third-world countries are at a higher risk of developing hypertension and its consequences for various reasons. If those at risk for HDP are detected early in the prenatal period, effective treatment can be given, and complications can be prevented.

Key words: hypertensive disorders, pregnancy

Introduction: Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) are among obstetrics' most intriguing and yet unsolved problem. HDP is blood pressure greater than or equal to 140/90 mmHg, with each measurement usually corroborating within 4 hours.¹ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the lethal trifecta of pregnancy are haemorrhage, HDP, and infection, which contribute significantly to maternal mortality and morbidity and claim the lives of at least one woman every 7 min.² These complicate up to 5–10% of pregnancies worldwide.³ Globally, the incidence of HDP has increased from 16.30 million to 18.08 million from 1990 to 2019, a total increase of 10.92% over two decades.⁴ The High Blood Pressure Education Program (2000) has classified HDP as gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia syndrome, and superimposed preeclampsia on chronic

hypertension. As per the reports from the National Health Portal, Government of India⁶ in 2016, the prevalence of HDP was 7.8% in India.

This study aims to estimate the prevalence of HDP in primiparous women and compare the prevalence of associated risk factors and pregnancy complications in primiparous women with and without HDP in a tertiary care centre in South Kerala, India. The current research is necessary since it is a realistic, cost-effective, simple and convenient way to reduce the scarcity of information about this topic in our population.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective analytical study was carried out at Pushpagiri Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre in Kerala, India, for 12 months, from December 2020 to December 2021. After taking permission from the institutional ethics committee, the study was ethically conducted as per the Declaration of Helsinki. Primigravidae of all ages who consented to the study and gave birth in the hospital during the study period were included. Women with multiple pregnancies, chronic hypertension, and missing clinical history (without proper antenatal records) were excluded from the study.

We have collected the prevalence, risk factors, pregnancy outcomes, and maternal and foetal outcomes from the patient's medical records. The variables analysed were the presence of hypertension, type of hypertension and potential risk factors: maternal age, educational status, income level, occupation, body mass index (BMI) at the first antenatal visit, family history of hypertension, history of smoking, in-vitro fertilisation (IVF) pregnancy, polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), and associated medical disorders (hyperglycaemia in pregnancy, renal disease, cardiac disease, collagen vascular disease, hypothyroidism). The pregnancy outcomes were evaluated by analysing the gestational age, mode of delivery and maternal and perinatal outcomes such as premature baby (a baby who delivers before 37 weeks).

Statistical Analysis: The study utilised the SPSS 18.0 software package to analyse the data. The association between the risk factors and HDP in primigravida was measured in terms of the ODDS ratio with a 95% confidence interval and tested for

significance using the Chi-square test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: A total of 807 primigravidae were included in the study, with 18.6% (150) having HDP. The mean age of participants was found to be 26.34 ± 3.84 years. Among the prevalent population, the study results showed that 79.3% (119) of women had gestational hypertension, 19.3% (29) had preeclampsia, and 1.3% (2) had eclampsia.

1) Association between socio-demographic factors and HDP

We compared the association of socio-demographic characteristics such as age, education, income level, occupation of the study subjects and social habits like smoking with HDP (Table 1). The results found that HDP was significantly associated with age group older than 40 ($p < 0.004$). Ages 18–39 years, income level, occupation, and smoking history were not associated with hypertensive disorders in pregnancy since the pvalue was greater than 0.05.

2) Risk factors associated with HDP

The study analysed the association between specific risk factors such as familial history, BMI of the mothers, IVF, disease conditions and HDP (Table 2). The findings indicate that HDP has a significant relationship with risk factors such as a family history of hypertension in pregnancy (of participant's mother or sisters) ($p < 0.001$), BMI of 18.5 kg/m² ($p < 0.002$), BMI >30 kg/m² ($p < 0.001$), IVF pregnancy ($p < 0.004$), hyperglycaemia in pregnancy ($p < 0.001$) and PCOS ($p < 0.001$)

3) Association of HDP with the mode of delivery and gestational age at delivery

The study also analysed the association of HDP with the mode of delivery and the gestational age at delivery (Table 3). While investigating the mode of delivery, it was found that preterm vaginal delivery ($p < 0.003$), preterm lower segment caesarean section(LSCS) ($p < 0.001$), and full-term LSCS ($p < 0.007$) have a significant relationship with the prevalence of HDP. In our study participants, the gestational age of delivery from 28 weeks to 36 weeks (preterm)was statistically significant for HDP with a p-value <0.001.

4) Adverse maternal and perinatal outcomes associated with HDP

All maternal complications of HDP studied in our study subjects like placental abruption ($p < 0.001$), postpartum haemorrhage ($p < 0.001$), thrombocytopenia/coagulopathy ($p < 0.001$), liver dysfunction ($p < 0.001$), renal dysfunction ($p < 0.001$), pulmonary oedema ($p < 0.003$), HELLP (Haemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, low platelet count) ($p < 0.001$) were found to have a statistically significant complication. Prematurity ($p < 0.001$) and FGR (fetal growth restriction) ($p < 0.001$) were among the most reported perinatal outcome

5) Association of PCOS and HDP

The study observed that PCOS is one of the risk factors for HDP, and among PCOS patients, pregnancy outcomes like gestational hypertension ($p < 0.001$), preeclampsia ($p < 0.001$), and hyperglycaemia in pregnancy ($p < 0.001$) were significant

Association between socio-demographic factors and HDP.

Socio-demographic variables	HDP n(%)		Total	OR (95% CI)	p value	
	Yes	No				
Age(Yrs)	<18	1(33.3)	2(66.7)	3	2.19(0.19-24.40)	<0.001*#
	19-29	98(15.1)	553(84.9)	651	0.35(0.23-0.52)	0.112
	30-39	46(31.9)	98(68.1)	144	2.52(1.67-3.79)	0.511
	>40	5(55.6)	4(44.4)	9	5.62(1.49-21.22)	0.004*#
Education	Primary School/Middle School	7(11.1)	56(88.9)	63	0.52(0.23-1.17)	0.112
	High School/Graduate	113(21)	425(79)	538	1.66(1.11-2.49)	0.613
	Post Graduate	30(14.6)	176(85.4)	206	0.68(0.44-1.05)	0.085
Income level	APL	77(18.1)	348(81.9)	425	0.93(0.65-1.33)	0.717
	BPL	73(19.1)	309(80.9)	382		
Occupation	Housewife	82(19.3)	342(80.7)	424	1.11(0.77-1.58)	0.563
	Govt Sector	20(18.7)	87(81.3)	107	1.00(0.59-1.69)	0.976
	Private Sector	48(17.4)	228(82.6)	276	0.88(0.60-1.29)	0.529
History of smoking	Yes	60(42)	83(58)	143	4.61(3.09-6.87)	<0.151
	No	90(13.6)	574(86.4)	664		

* p-value significant. # p-value shows significance, but the sample size is less to predict the exact relationship.H0: There is no association between socio-demographic factors and HDP, H1: There is an association between socio-demographic factors and HDP.

Note:HDP: Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy; APL: Above Poverty Line; BPL: Below poverty line; Yrs: years.

Risk Factors associated with HDP.

Variables		HDP n(%)		Total	OR (95% CI)	p-value
		Yes	No			
Family history of hypertension in pregnancy	Yes	87(37.3)	146(62.7)	233	4.83(3.32-7.01)	<0.001*
	No	63(11)	511(89)	574		
BMI	<18.5	4(8.3)	44(91.7)	48	0.38(0.13-1.07)	0.341
	18.5-24.9	58(14.3)	348(85.7)	406	0.56(0.39-0.80)	0.06
	25-29.9	44(16.7)	220(83.3)	264	0.82(0.56-1.21)	0.328
	>30	44(49.4)	45(50.6)	89	5.64(3.55-8.87)	<0.001*
IVF pregnancy	Yes	5(55.6)	4(44.4)	9	5.62(1.49-21.22)	0.004*
	No	145(18.2)	653(81.8)	798		
Hyperglycaemia in pregnancy	Yes	75(28.6)	187(71.4)	262	2.51(1.75-3.61)	<0.001*
	No	75(13.8)	470(86.2%)	545		
Pre-existing renal disease	Yes	0	1(100)	1	1.22(1.18-1.27)	0.633
	No	150(18.6)	656(81.4)	806		
Pre-existing cardiac disease	Yes	1(9.1)	10(90.9)	11	0.43(0.05-3.41)	0.415
	No	149(18.7)	647(81.3)	796		
Pre-existing collagen vascular disease	Yes	3(42.9)	4(57.1)	7	3.33(0.73-15.04)	0.097
	No	147(18.4)	653(81.6)	800		
Hypothyroidism	Yes	47(26.9)	128(73.1)	175	1.88(1.27-2.80)	0.211
	No	103(16.3)	529(83.7)	632		
PCOS	Yes	150 (57)	111(43)	261	2.51(1.75-3.61)	<0.001*
	No	34 (6.3)	512 (93.7)	546		

*p value significant; Note: BMI: Body mass index, IVF: In vitro fertilisation, PCOS: Polycystic ovary syndrome.

Association of HDP with mode of delivery and gestational age at delivery.

Variables		HDP n(%)		Total	OR (95% CI)	p value
		Yes	No			
Mode of delivery	FTVD	61(11.8)	457(88.2)	518	0.30(0.20-0.43)	0.522
	PTVD	15(35.7)	27(64.3)	42	2.59(1.34-5.00)	0.003*
	Assisted birth	6(15.8)	32(84.2)	38	0.81(0.33-1.98)	0.65
	Full term LSCS	42(25.9)	120(74.1)	162	1.74(1.15-2.61)	0.007*
	Preterm LSCS	26(55.3)	21(44.7)	47	6.35(3.46-11.64)	<0.001*
Gestational age at delivery	<28 Weeks	0	6(100)	6	1.23(1.19-1.27)	0.24
	28-33 Weeks	11(47.8)	12(52.2)	23	4.25(1.83-9.83)	<0.001*
	34-36 Weeks	30(51.7)	28(48.3)	58	5.61(3.23-9.74)	<0.001*
	≥37 Weeks	109(15.1)	611(84.9)	720	0.20(0.12-0.32)	0.084

*p value significant; H0: There is no association between HDP and Mode of delivery & GA at delivery. H1: There is an association between HDP and Mode of delivery & GA at delivery.

Note: FTVD: Full term vaginal delivery, PTVD: Preterm vaginal delivery, LSCS: Lower segment cesarian section, Assisted birth: A forceps or a ventouse suction cup are used to help delivery the baby.

Adverse maternal and perinatal complications associated with Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

Complications	HDP n(%)		Total	OR (95% CI)	p value
	Yes	No			
Placental Abruption	5(100)	0	5	5.50(4.74-6.36)	<0.001*
Postpartum Haemorrhage	9(75)	3(25)	12	13.91(3.72-15.05)	<0.001*
Thrombocytopenia/Coagulopathy	3(100)	0	3	5.46(4.72-6.33)	<0.001*
Liver Disfunction	3(100)	0	3	5.46(4.72-6.33)	<0.001*
Renal Disfunction	3(100)	0	3	5.46(4.72-6.33)	<0.001*
Pulmonary Oedema	2(100)	0	2	5.43(4.70-6.29)	0.003*
HELLP	3(100)	0	3	5.46(4.72-6.33)	<0.001*
PREMATURITY	35(48.6)	37(51.4)	72	5.10(3.08-8.43)	<0.001*
FGR	25(27.5)	66(72.5)	91	1.79(1.08-2.95)	0.021*
IUFD	3(37.5)	5(62.5)	8	2.66(0.62-11.26)	0.167
NND	1(25)	3(75)	4	1.46(0.15-14.16)	0.741

*p value significant.

Note: HELLP: Hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, and low platelets; FGR: Fetal growth restriction; IUFD: intrauterine fetal demise; NND: neonatal death. All maternal complications are statistically significant and in perinatal outcomes FGR and prematurity were clinically significant.

Pregnancy complications in PCOS and Non PCOS women.

Pregnancy complication	Total Patients	PCOS n(%)	Non-PCOS n(%)	p Value
Gestational hypertension	80	53 (66)	27 (34)	<0.001*
Preeclampsia	86	57 (66)	29 (34)	<0.001*
Eclampsia	2	1 (50)	1 (50)	0.44
Gestational diabetes mellitus	196	150 (77)	46 (23)	<0.001*

*p value significant, PCOS: Polycystic ovary syndrome.

Conclusion: In summary, our study looked at the risk factors and pregnancy outcomes following HDP and found that the risk factors studied, like extremes of age, family history of HDP, increased BMI, IVF pregnancy, hyperglycaemia in pregnancy and PCOS, have a substantial correlation with HDP. HDPs are on the rise in India, and they contribute to maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality in a significant way. From this study, we emphasise the importance of knowledge and timely assessment of risk factors of HDP. Proper interventions with the right treatment can help reduce maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity and their longterm effects. However, there are currently no well-established measures for predicting or preventing HDP. So, the study highlights the need for pre-conceptual counselling, which includes early detection, careful monitoring and treatment of HDP to prevent morbidity and mortality related to this disorder. It should be followed up even in the postpartum period.

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